

PROV-SwProcess DISCREPANT CASES

Associations Discrepant Cases

PROV-SwProcess uses associations between classes to represent both prospective and retrospective provenance. An association occurs between two classes, always having a source (domain) and a destination (range). Associations DCs are listed from **DC.01** to **DC.22**.

A. Software Process Associations

A *Software Process* represents a software development process in its entirety and has the following associations: *wasAttributedTo*, *wasComposedBy* and *wasDerivedFrom* to capture retrospective provenance and the association *isComposedBy* to capture prospective provenance.

Omission

DC.01 Some association needed to describe a performed software process (in addition to *wasAttributedTo*, *wasComposedBy* and *wasDerivedFrom*) was omitted from the model.

DC.02 Some association needed to describe the prospective provenance of a software process (in addition to *isComposedBy*) was omitted from the model.

Incorrect fact

DC.03 Some software process association is not compliant with software development process.

Inconsistency

DC.04 Some software process association has the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model).

Ambiguity

DC.05 Some software process association is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms.

Extraneous information

DC.06 Some software process association does not belong to the provenance of software development process.

B. Activity Associations

An Activity represents a computational task in the software development process. It can be atomic or composed by other sub-activities.

Omission

DC.07 Some association needed to describe the activities that were performed in a software development process (in addition to *wasAssociatedWith*, *hadSubActivity*, *wasInformedBy*, *adopted*, *changed*, *used*, *startedAtTime*, *endedAtTime*) was omitted from the model.

DC.08 Some association needed to describe the activities to be executed in a software development process (in addition to *precedes*, *dependsOn*, *hasSubActivity*) was omitted from the model.

Incorrect fact

DC.09 Some activity association is not compliant with software development process.

Inconsistency

DC.10 Some activity association has the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model).

Ambiguity

DC.11 Some activity association is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms.

Extraneous information

DC.12 Some activity association does not belong to the provenance of software development process.

C. Stakeholder Associations

A Stakeholder represents an agent involved, interested, or affected by the software process activities. It can be specialized in other four types: (i) Organization Stakeholder, (ii) Person Stakeholder, (iii) Project Stakeholder, and (iv) Team Stakeholder.

Omission

DC.13 Some association needed to describe the relation between stakeholders in a software development process (in addition to *actedOnBehalfOf*) was omitted from the model.

Incorrect fact

DC.14 The stakeholder association is not compliant with software development process.

Inconsistency

DC.15 The stakeholder association has the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model) of another model association.

Ambiguity

DC.16 The stakeholder association is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms.

Extraneous information

DC.17 The stakeholder association does not belong to the provenance of software development process.

D. Artifact Associations

Artifacts represent the objects produced, changed, or used in the software development process activities. Artifacts can be of five types: (i) Software_Product, (ii) Software_Item, (iii) Document, (iv) Model, and (v) Information_Item.

Omission

DC.18 Some association whose origin is a software process artifact (in addition to *wasGeneratedBy*, *wasAttributedTo* and *wasDerivedFrom*) was omitted from the model.

Incorrect fact

DC.19 Some artifact association is not compliant with software development process.

Inconsistency

DC.20 Some artifact association has the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model).

Ambiguity

DC.21 Some artifact association is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms.

Extraneous information

DC.22 Some artifact association does not belong to the provenance of software development process.

Classes Discrepant Cases

PROV-SwProcess has 20 classes to represent the provenance of Software Development Process. These classes are divided into five specific aspects, as shown in Table 1. Classes DCs are listed from **DC.23** to **DC.27**.

Table 1. PROV-SwProcess Classes

PROV-SwProcess Aspect	Class Name
Activity	Activity
	Software_Process
Stakeholder	Stakeholder
	Organization_Stakeholder
	Person_Stakeholder
	Project_Stakeholder
	Team_Stakeholder
Resource	Resource
	Software_Resource
	Hardware_Resource
Procedure	Procedure
	Method
	Document_Template
	Technique
Artifact	Artifact
	Software_Product
	Software_Item
	Document
	Model
	Information_Item

Omission

DC.23 Some class needed to describe the provenance of software development process (in addition to the classes in Table 1), was omitted from the model.

Incorrect fact

DC.24 Some class is not compliant with software development process.

Inconsistency

DC.25 Some class has the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model).

Ambiguity

DC.26 Some class is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms.

Extraneous information

DC.27 Some class does not belong to the modeling software process domain.

Inferences Discrepant cases

PROV-SwProcess has six specific inference rules. Considering an inference as a rule that can be applied to PROV-SwProcess instances to add new PROV-SwProcess statements, **DC.28** to **DC.32** are created to deal with these inference rules.

Omission

DC.28 Some inference rule needed to describe the provenance of software development process was omitted from the model.

Incorrect fact

DC.29 Some inference rule is not compliant with software development process.

Inconsistency

DC.30 Some inference rule has the same semantic meaning (is duplicated in the model).

Ambiguity

DC.31 Some inference rule is not clearly described, using ambiguous terms.

Extraneous information

DC.32 Some inference rule does not belong to the modeling software process domain.